

TRANSMIND: MINDFULNESS-BASED INTERVENTION FOR TRANSGENDER AND GENDER-DIVERSE INDIVIDUALS

Prepared for
Radboudumc Expertisecentrum voor Geslacht & Gender
Supervisor: Dr. G. Collin
Guusje.Collin@radboudumc.nl
Psychiatry Department, Radboudumc

By
Skorobogatova, E.V. (Ekaterina)
S1049452
Ekaterina.Skorobogatova@radboudumc.nl

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Letter of Transmittal

As agreed, I am submitting the attached advisory report titled “TransMind: Mindfulness-Based Intervention for Transgender and Gender-Diverse Individuals”. This advisory report was written in the context of my involvement in the TransMind pilot study, which explores the potential benefits of mindfulness training on body awareness and emotion regulation among transgender and gender-diverse (TGD) individuals.

It has been a pleasure to contribute to a project so closely aligned with my values and academic interests. This memorandum not only summarizes the research as conducted during the pilot phase but also includes recommendations for adjusting the study procedures and design in preparation for the upcoming larger-scale research. These recommendations are informed by insights gathered throughout the pilot and aim to better “tailor” the intervention to the community's needs while minimizing participant burden.

I would like to thank all those involved in the development and supervision of the TransMind project, and I am especially grateful for the opportunity to have contributed to this work.

Please don't hesitate to reach out if you require any further information or clarification. I hope this report meets your expectations and supports the continued development of this important research.

Sincerely,
Kate Skorobogatova

Executive Summary

Transgender and gender-diverse (TGD) individuals in the Netherlands face extreme barriers to accessing healthcare. In the past five years, demand for transgender care has increased fivefold, and waiting times have escalated from just over one year to between three and six years. These delays have severe psychosocial and physical consequences, including anxiety, depression, suicidality, and self-medication with hormones. TGD individuals, particularly youth, are among the most vulnerable groups when it comes to mental health, which makes these risks even more pronounced. Yet, despite the magnitude of the problem, there are currently no generally accessible or routinely offered forms of structured psychosocial support for individuals on waiting lists.

This report explores the potential of a mindfulness-based intervention (MBI), specifically Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy for Life (MBCT-L), as a structured form of support for TGD individuals awaiting gender-affirming care. MBIs are an evidence-based approach to reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety while improving mental health and resilience. To assess feasibility, a pilot study was conducted with individuals who had already accessed transgender care and previously experienced being on a waiting list, ensuring participants could reflect on the relevance of the training without being dependent on the study.

The results of this pilot were encouraging. All participants completed the mindfulness training program and were generally positive about the experience. They reported improved emotion regulation, greater awareness of their bodies, and an increased ability to express emotions constructively. Many also valued the group format, where shared experiences created a validating and supportive environment. At the same time, participants raised concerns about potential drawbacks, such as the strictness of homework requirements, feelings of guilt when unable to complete exercises, and fears that mindfulness might become a replacement rather than a complement to gender-affirming treatment. Importantly, some participants experienced certain practices, such as the body scan, as triggering. These findings underline the need to adapt the training format to transgender-specific experiences and to ensure the presence of a clinically trained facilitator alongside a TGD trainer. A clinician would be able to recognize and respond to participants experiencing heightened mental health difficulties, which are expected to be more prevalent among those currently on the wait list.

Building on these insights, the report recommends a second pilot with participants currently on the Radboudumc waiting list, followed by a larger randomized controlled trial. Adaptations to the program should include incorporating discussions relevant to transgender lived experiences, careful consideration of potentially triggering exercises, and addressing ethical aspects of data collection. In particular, participants in the pilot study raised concerns about being required to provide their legal names (“deadnames”) on informed consent forms, which are stored for 15 years. More affirming and flexible practices are needed to avoid distress and ensure trust.

The current pilot demonstrates promising potential for MBCT-L as a psychosocial support measure for TGD individuals facing extended waiting times. While further adaptation and testing are necessary, this approach offers a realistic and evidence-based way to mitigate the psychological harm caused by delays in accessing gender-affirming care and improve mental health and resilience of TGD individuals.

Background of the problem

The client's inquiry

The [Radboudumc Expertise Center for Sex & Gender](#) (English for Radboudumc Expertisecentrum voor Geslacht & Gender, REGG) is facing significant challenges due to the rapidly increasing number of requests for transgender care. As a result, waiting times have sharply increased and continue to grow. Concerned about the mental health and well-being of individuals on their wait list, the client seeks ways to provide effective support during this period of prolonged waiting.

In discussions with the client prior to the start of the project, the following goals were identified:

1. **The long-term goal of the client is to provide mental health support** to individuals on the wait list for transgender care within the REGG.
2. **To this end, the client seeks to conduct a pilot study** that explores the effects of the mindfulness-based intervention on emotion and body awareness, while offering insights into the feasibility of the chosen measures.
3. **The aim of this pilot study is to develop recommendations** on a larger-scale study on MBIs as a support option for people on the wait list for transgender care.

To address these objectives, it was agreed that a pilot study would be carried out. This pilot serves both as a response to the client's inquiries and as a means to gather practical experience and knowledge that can inform future recommendations. Consequently, the findings and outcomes of the study are interwoven throughout this advisory report to illustrate the broader problem and potential approaches.

Disclaimer: As will become clear, the underlying issue concerns the general dissatisfaction of the transgender population with the current transgender healthcare system. Addressing this issue in its entirety lies far beyond the scope of this project, as it would require fundamental changes not only to the system itself but also to societal understanding and perceptions of transgender identities. For this reason, this project deliberately narrows its focus to exploring ways of supporting transgender individuals during their time on a wait list—aiming to reduce potential mental health deterioration during this period.

Overview problem situation

The transgender population in the Netherlands faces severe challenges in accessing timely healthcare. Long waiting lists, poor communication, and limited provider knowledge contribute to uncertainty and significant psychological strain.

Waiting for care has been described as one of the most difficult aspects of the medical transition process, with consequences including feelings of panic, hopelessness, and standstill in daily life and psychosocial development (Linander & Alm, 2022). TGD populations already show higher baseline rates of depression, anxiety, self-harm, and suicidality. Prolonged delays further worsen these outcomes being linked to lower mood, decreased quality of life, and increased suicidal ideation. (Henderson et al.,

2022; van de Grift et al., 2024). Faced with multiple barriers to accessing formal transgender healthcare – including financial obstacles, stigma from society and clinicians, in addition to prolonged waiting times (August-Rae et al., 2024; J. T. Baker et al., 2023; Mepham et al., 2014) - some individuals resort to self-medicating with hormones, which carries health risks due to incorrect dosing, including an increased risk of blood clots, liver enzyme abnormalities, etc. (Bourns, 2023; U.S. Food & Drug administration, 2025), or usage of unregulated, potentially counterfeit, products (Henderson et al., 2022).

A consistent finding is the urgent need for psychosocial support during waiting times, as the absence of routine support leaves many feeling isolated and without perspective (Linander & Alm, 2022).

Improving Body and Emotional Awareness as a Way to Prevent and Alleviate Mental Health Deterioration

As discussed above, TGD individuals experience heightened distress, which can contribute to or exacerbate mental health difficulties. The co-occurrence of gender dysphoria (GD) and mental health problems may stem from minority stress, lack of social support and acceptance, and (self-)stigma. An additional factor is possibly impaired interoceptive ability—the capacity to detect, interpret, and integrate bodily signals—which plays a central role in emotional awareness and regulation. For those whose internal experience of their body does not align with their gender identity, or who do not feel “at home” in their body, this ability can be compromised, making it harder to recognize and manage emotions effectively.

Mindfulness-based interventions (MBIs) have been shown to improve emotion regulation, reduce symptoms of depression and anxiety (Goldberg et al., 2018), and strengthen interoceptive ability (Buric et al., 2024; Lazzarelli et al., 2024). By fostering non-judgmental awareness of bodily sensations and emotional states, MBIs may help TGD individuals reconnect with their bodies, increase their ability to recognize and work with their emotions, and develop healthier coping strategies. This makes MBIs a promising approach both as an add-on to gender-affirming treatment and as a preventive measure to support well-being during extended waiting periods.

Prior efforts to solve the problem

Despite the known challenges faced by TGD individuals awaiting care, few formal initiatives have been implemented in the REGG to support this population during their waiting periods. The center’s primary focus has understandably been on providing as many TGD individuals as possible with access to gender-affirming care, which has limited the capacity for developing psychosocial support structures in parallel with their main course of action. Below, the main efforts that have been made so far, as well as their limitations, are outlined.

1. Waiting List Mediation

Generally speaking, wait list mediation is a service offered by health insurers to clients who face excessively long waiting times for medical treatment. This may involve the

insurer arranging an appointment at another facility. However, given that specialized centers for transgender healthcare across the country are overloaded by rapidly increasing demand, wait list mediation does not seem like a viable option to mitigate the distress associated with the wait.

2. Supporting Individuals on the Waiting Lists Instead

Given the difficulty in shortening waiting times directly, some attention has turned to supporting people while they wait.

a. "[*De Warme Wachtkamer*](#)" (*The Warm Waiting Room*)

This initiative, launched by the Humanist Association, aimed to offer support to individuals during their waiting period for transgender healthcare. However, its reach and effectiveness were limited due to several factors:

- The initiative was part of an older policy plan, and it remains unclear whether it will be included in the new strategic direction of the Humanist Association.
- Hospitals often refer patients to their own internal spiritual caregivers rather than to external ones like those involved in the Warm Waiting Room.
- Many general practitioners are unaware of the initiative and therefore do not refer patients, limiting its visibility and use.

Note on Community-Based Support

Outside of official channels, efforts within the transgender community—such as peer groups, online forums, and safe spaces like the [Transgender Café in Nijmegen](#) — play a meaningful role in providing informal support. While these initiatives are vital to many individuals' resilience, they lie beyond the scope of this report, which focuses on formal healthcare system responses. Nonetheless, their existence highlights the ongoing need for institutional support structures that meet the psychological and social needs of people on the waiting list.

Significance of the problem

Current policy

In the Netherlands, the process of accessing transgender healthcare typically begins with an individual recognizing persistent feelings of gender incongruence and consulting a general practitioner (GP). If the GP is supportive and knowledgeable, they provide a referral to a gender care center. From that point, individuals are placed on a waiting list, which currently spans between three to six years depending on the clinic. During this period, there is usually no structured psychological support or regular communication from the care providers. Once an intake is scheduled, the individual undergoes a diagnostic phase that can last several months, involving multiple assessments to evaluate gender identity and mental health. Only after this phase do

they gain access to medical treatments such as hormone therapy or surgery — often years after their initial referral.

Assess the scope and severity of the problem

The waiting times for transgender healthcare in the Netherlands have grown significantly in recent years. While most transgender care centers no longer publish estimated waiting durations, they now display the dates of referral they are currently contacting. As of July 2025, these referral dates range from January 2021 to February 2022 in the larger centers, indicating waiting times of three to four years. According to van de Grift et al. (2024), average waiting times in 2019 already exceeded one year. In 2024–2025, these times have extended further, with some individuals waiting up to six years to receive a diagnosis or begin gender-affirming treatment. In many countries, including the Netherlands, these waiting periods exceed the legal or policy-based standards set for access to healthcare, set at 14 weeks for non-acute mental healthcare and 4–7 weeks for hospital care.

Compared to other areas of medicine, the waiting times for transgender care are disproportionately long. At Radboudumc’s Amalia Children’s Hospital, [waiting periods](#) for general pediatrics, cardiology, and neurology typically range between 19 and 73 days. In contrast, access to transgender care for youth can take approximately 900 days. Similar disparities are present in adult transgender care departments. This disparity in treatment timelines can be explained by the requirement for a psychological assessment to obtain a gender dysphoria diagnosis. In the Netherlands, waiting times for psychological care are exceptionally long, which significantly delays access to gender-affirming treatment.

The affected population has also grown in size. Estimates from 2019 indicated around 34,000 TGD individuals in the Netherlands (in or awaiting care, van de Grift et al., 2024). As of 2023, this number is estimated to be approximately 196,000 (151,000 transgender and 45,000 non-binary/gender queer) ([CBS](#)), reflecting approximately a sixfold increase in individuals identifying as non-cisgender. This rise in demand for care, combined with limited system capacity, contributes to the limited possibilities for timely access to transgender healthcare. It should be noted that not all TGD individuals seek medical transition, but available data suggest that a substantial proportion do. For instance, a 2019 study in the United States reported that approximately 65% of transgender individuals in an insurance database were receiving gender-affirming hormone therapy (K. Baker & Restar, 2022). Even though more recent estimates are limited, this figure indicates that a significant share of the population requires medical support.

Problem statement

Diagnose problem

The core issue addressed in this project is the psychological burden experienced by TGD individuals during excessively long waiting periods for access to gender-affirming healthcare (GAH) in the Netherlands. These waiting times often extend well beyond

legal and clinical norms—frequently reaching three to six years—leaving individuals in a state of prolonged uncertainty and psychological distress.

This delay is not only a logistical bottleneck in the healthcare system but also a mental health crisis in itself. The extended waiting period is associated with heightened rates of depression, anxiety, suicidality, emotional dysregulation, and a sense of social and medical abandonment, as shown in prior literature and confirmed by interviewees in the current pilot study. Despite the severity of the issue, there are currently no scalable, evidence-based support structures in place to care for individuals during this waiting period.

This pilot project—the beginning of the TransMind initiative—aims to explore feasible, low-barrier psychological interventions (specifically mindfulness-based support) that can be offered during the waiting period to reduce mental health deterioration in TGD individuals. At the same time, it generates feedback to improve the research design and support models for a future, larger-scale implementation.

In essence, the advisory report targets the systemic gap in care during the waiting period and seeks to provide both immediate and long-term recommendations for mitigating its impact on well-being.

Describe major stakeholders

The issue of prolonged waiting times for gender-affirming healthcare affects and implicates a broad network of stakeholders. Each group has a distinct role in the current situation, the pilot study, and the potential implementation of solutions:

1. **Transgender and Gender-Diverse (TGD) Individuals**

This group is the primary stakeholder, as they are directly affected by the long waiting periods. The prolonged lack of access to care contributes to significant emotional distress, reduced well-being, and increased psychological risk. Their lived experiences, both during the waiting time and in response to interventions such as mindfulness training, are central to understanding the problem and co-developing solutions.

2. **Family/Friends/Loved ones**

Family members, partners, and friends play a central role in the well-being of TGD individuals, particularly during extended waiting periods for gender-affirming care. They often serve as the primary source of emotional, social, and sometimes financial support. However, the prolonged uncertainty and distress experienced by the TGD individual can also have a significant psychological impact on their loved ones. These stakeholders may face their own stress, anxiety, and feelings of helplessness, as well as challenges in navigating healthcare systems and understanding the complexities of gender dysphoria. Effective interventions that support TGD individuals indirectly benefit their support networks, helping to reduce relational strain and strengthen the resilience of the entire social environment surrounding the individual.

3. **Healthcare Providers**

This includes:

- Psychologists and psychiatrists responsible for diagnosing gender dysphoria and determining eligibility and fitness for gender-affirming treatments.
- Mindfulness Trainers and mental health care providers who may facilitate support programs like MBCT-L.
- General Practitioners and other clinicians who are often the first point of contact and must support patients through extended waiting periods despite limited resources and training.

These professionals are often caught in the systemic bottleneck and are key to implementing any interim or structural improvements.

4. **REGG (Radboudumc Expertisecentrum voor Geslacht & Gender/ Radboudumc Center of Expertise on Sex & Gender)**

In this pilot study, the REGG is the institutional partner hosting the TransMind initiative. As such, it has a dual role: as both a site of the problem (due to overloaded systems and long waiting times) and as a potential innovator of solutions. The outcomes of this study may inform their future policy or care offerings.

5. **Health Insurance Providers**

Insurance companies play a crucial role in enabling access to gender-affirming care, including hormone treatments, surgeries, and potentially mental health support programs, such as the MBCT-L. Their willingness to reimburse such preventive or supportive interventions could determine whether these services can be scaled or standardized in the future.

6. **Funding Associations and Grant Providers**

While not stakeholders in the problem per se, these organizations are key to the feasibility and continuity of initiatives like TransMind. Their involvement reflects institutional interest in innovation and inclusivity in mental health care, and their decisions influence what types of research and pilot programs can be developed and sustained.

7. **Ministry of Health, Welfare and Sport (VWS)**

As the government body responsible for healthcare policy in the Netherlands, the Ministry holds ultimate responsibility for equitable access to care. The current mismatch between legal standards and real-world waiting times falls under their purview, making them critical stakeholders in systemic reform and broader adoption of supportive interventions.

Goals and objectives

The primary goal of this advisory report is to provide a concise, evidence-based summary of the findings from the TransMind pilot study, aimed at supporting the REGG in implementing a new, structured approach to support TGD individuals currently on waiting lists for specialized gender-affirming treatment.

More specifically, the objectives of this report are to:

- Confirm findings from the literature by examining the lived experiences of individuals from the local area while on the waiting list, with a focus on the availability (or absence) of support.
- Present insights from the pilot study to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of a mindfulness-based intervention as a supportive measure during waiting times.
- Support the development of a multi-step implementation, including:
 - Tailoring the protocol and workbook of the MBCT-L program to the needs to TGD individuals based on the results of the current pilot study.
 - A second pilot phase in a sample of participants who are currently on the waiting list at the REGG, to confirm feasibility and acceptability in the target population and estimate effect sizes for the larger trial
 - A larger-scale, well-powered Randomized Controlled Trial (RCT) in individuals on the REGG waiting list.

The pilot study

Design

The following section describes the design of the pilot study that forms the basis of this advisory report. The descriptions below are partly derived from the research protocol, which was developed with contributions from the advisor for this project.

Population

This pilot study focuses on TGD individuals who have already received some form of transgender healthcare, such as gender-affirming hormone therapy (GAHT) or surgical procedures, and who have socially transitioned. This population was chosen primarily for ethical/safety concerns because they are in a less vulnerable position compared to individuals who are still waiting for care. They already have access to transgender healthcare and can provide open, constructive feedback on both the mindfulness training and the research procedures. For participants on the waitlist, additional care will need to be taken to clearly communicate that their decision to participate or the nature of their responses will in no way affect their access to transgender healthcare at the REGG. The participants were competent adults between the ages of 18 and 50, with up to mild current mental health problems.

Gender		% (n)
Gender assigned at birth	Male	100 (8)
Gender identity	Woman	87,5 (7)
	Non-binary	12,5 (1)
Age		Mean (SD)
Range (21 - 39)		27 (6)
Mental/Neurodivergency diagnosis		% (n)
Previous diagnosis	Gender dysphoria	87,5 (7)
	Autism	25 (2)
	Generalized Anxiety Disorder	12,5 (1)
	Clinical Depression	12,5 (1)
	PTSD	12,5 (1)
Self-suspected Neurodivergency	Autism	12,5 (1)
	AD(H)D	25 (2)
Education		% (n)
Achieved	Secondary school; Entrance qualified for Universities	50 (4)
	University or University of Applied Sciences Bachelor	50 (4)
Current	No education	62,5 (5)
	University or University of Applied Sciences Bachelor	37,5 (3)
Employment		% (n)
	Unemployed	25 (2)
	Full-time student	50 (1)
	Part-time	37,5 (3)
	Full-time	12,5 (1)
	Side job (next to studies)	25 (2)
Friends		% (n)
Close friend	2 or 3	25 (2)
	4 or more	75 (6)
Contact each month	3 or 4 times	12,5 (1)
	5 or more times	87,5 (7)
Mindfulness		% (n)
Previously participated in a training	Yes	25 (2)
	No	75 (6)
Currently practices mindfulness/meditation	Yes	12,5 (1)
	No	87,5 (7)
Treatment		% (n)
Hormone replacement therapy (HRT)		100 (8)
Substance use		% (n)
Smoke cigarettes	Yes	0 (0)
	No	100 (8)
Vape	Yes	0 (0)
	No	100 (8)

Alcohol	Yes		62,5 (5)
	Drinks per week	Less than 1	40 (2)
		1 to 3	60 (3)
	No		37,5 (3)

Table 1. Demographic table describing the participants of the first pilot.

General Design

The pilot study combined qualitative and quantitative data collection to assess feasibility and acceptability of group-based MBCT-L training co-facilitated by a trainer with lived experience and explore body awareness and emotion regulation as putative targets of intervention. It consisted of pre- and post-intervention semi-structured interviews and a set of questionnaires administered at three time points (baseline, mid-point, and post-intervention). Additionally, participants participated in an 8-week mindfulness-based intervention (MBI) adapted in language for the TGD population. Participants were recruited through TGD networks. The aim was to gather qualitative insights into the participants' experiences, alongside preliminary quantitative data, to evaluate the feasibility and acceptability of the intervention and the research design.

Figure 2. The protocol timeline of the TransMind pilot study #1.

The Mindfulness Program

The mindfulness training offered was the Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy for Life (MBCT-L) program, developed by the University of Oxford Mindfulness Centre. The program was adapted in terms of language and examples to ensure inclusivity for a gender-diverse population. It was delivered by two trainers, one of whom had lived TGD experience and the other a clinician and registered mindfulness trainer. The training consisted of eight weekly two-hour group sessions and one silent day (10 AM – 4 PM). The program incorporated formal mindfulness practices, psychoeducation, elements of cognitive therapy, and gentle physical exercises. Participants were encouraged to practice at home for approximately 30 minutes per day.

Session #	Theme	Introduced topics	Introduced exercises
1	Waking up from the automatic pilot	Attitudes that can support mindfulness practice	Body scan, ten finger gratitude exercise, doing one routine activity mindfully
2	Another way of being: keeping the body in mind	Power of interpretation, the interplay of thoughts, emotions, body sensations and impulses, anchor point	50:50 attention division between body and speaking or listening, sitting with breath, experiences calendar (positive)
3	Gathering the Scattered mind	Physical boundaries, staying present	3-step breathing space, mindful movement, experiences calendar (negative)
4	Recognizing reactivity	The vicious flower, becoming conscious of autopilot reactions (helpful and unhelpful)	Daily walking practice, working wisely with reactivity
5	Allowing and Letting be	Peacefully facing the difficulties, allowing yourself to be with the difficulty	Random acts of kindness
Silent day	N/A	Many topics from the course	Collection of many exercises, mindful walk in nature, silent lunch
6	Responding skillfully: thoughts are not facts	Compassion for yourself, ways to see thoughts differently	Choose own set of exercises for 40 minutes of daily practicing
7	How can I best take care of myself?	Learning about nourishing and depleting activities in own routine, exhaustion funnel	Establish a pattern of daily practice to follow for the next 2-3 months
8	Mindfulness for Life	Motivation, tips for sustaining mindfulness	N/A

Table 2. The contents of the Mindfulness for Life program used in the pilot study.

Semi-Structured Interviews (Appendix 2)

Two qualitative interviews were conducted with each participant—one before and one after the mindfulness intervention—each lasting approximately 30 to 40 minutes.

- Pre-intervention interviews explored participants’ experiences during waiting times for transgender care (e.g., “Can you tell us about your experience being on the waiting list for specialized transgender care?”), as well as their current relationship with their body and approaches to emotion regulation (e.g., “How would you describe your relationship with your body?” and “How do you cope with emotions?”).
- Post-intervention interviews repeated the questions about body and emotion awareness to assess potential changes resulting from the mindfulness program. They also focused on participants’ feedback regarding the MBCT-L training, the group format, and the overall research procedures.

Questionnaires

Participants completed a set of 11 questionnaires at three timepoints: baseline (T0), mid-point (T1), and post-intervention (T2). These questionnaires assessed body awareness, mindfulness skills, emotional awareness and regulation, and psychological well-being. The quantitative data collected through these questionnaires will help to evaluate the potential effects of the intervention and inform the design of future studies.

Measurements	T0	T1	T2
Demographic and clinical assessment			
Demographics	T0		
DSM-5 Self-Rated Level 1 Cross-Cutting Symptom Measure-Adult (DSM XC)	T0		
Body Awareness			
Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA)	T0	T1	T2
Emotional Awareness and Regulation			
Difficulties in Emotional Regulation Scale (DERS)	T0	T1	T2
Perth Alexithymia Questionnaire (PAQ)	T0	T1	T2
Psychological well-being			
Rumination Reflection Questionnaire (RRQ)	T0	T1	T2
Perceived Stress Scale (PSS)	T0	T1	T2
Positive and Negative Affect (PANAS)	T0	T1	T2
Mindfulness skills			
Five Facets Mindfulness Questionnaire (FFMQ)	T0	T1	T2
Self-Compassion Scale (SCS)	T0	T1	T2
Experiences Questionnaire (EQ decentering subscale)	T0	T1	T2

Table 3. Overview of the questionnaires used in the pilot study. T0 – baseline (0-2 weeks before the intervention), T1 – intervention mid-point, T2- 0-2 weeks after the intervention.

Summary of the preliminary results

This section provides a summary of the pilot study results for both the qualitative and quantitative components, based on the data analyzed to date. For the quantitative component, only the primary findings and observable trends are presented here; a detailed analysis can be found in the report prepared by M. Horning. All figures in this section were produced by M. Horning.

Participation experience

Participant engagement was high, with full attendance across the training and all participants completing more than four sessions.

Overall, participants reported very positive experiences with both the intervention and the study. Several described the training as *“genuinely a helpful thing”* and *“a really surprisingly good experience.”* Many highlighted its value in reducing feelings of being overwhelmed and in providing practical strategies for everyday life. As one participant explained, *“It’s useful because it makes the rest of your life less overwhelming and it makes it so that you can become more aware of your emotions.”*

A common theme was the sense that the program could function as an important form of support during the waiting period. One participant reflected, *“I can very much imagine that it helps because they’re at least getting some kind of therapy in a way already... they’re learning to deal with their emotions, but they’re also learning to understand themselves better.”*

The group format was described as particularly meaningful, fostering connection, validation, and safety. As one participant shared, *“I felt like I was in a safe enough space to share my experiences.”* Another noted, *“The group setting is very nice because you have a way of connecting with people. And because you are treating other people as valid, you start treating yourself as valid as well.”*

Finally, participants emphasized that the training offered them concrete tools and new perspectives: *“I’ve learned a lot of tools and not just exercises, but also ways of thinking or ways of reframing whatever problem I’m dealing with.”*

Together, these reflections suggest that participants experienced the intervention not only as supportive and safe but also as equipping them with skills that extended beyond the training sessions.

Concerns Following the Mindfulness Course

Despite the overall positive experiences, participants also voiced several concerns regarding the mindfulness course. A critical one was the fear of how the intervention might be positioned within the broader care system. Participants expressed apprehension that mindfulness training could be seen as *“another hoop to jump through”* before gaining access to medical treatment. Others worried that it might be

misinterpreted as a substitute for gender-affirming care, such as hormones or other medical interventions, rather than as a complementary form of support.

Another recurring issue was the perceived rigidity of the homework structure. Some worried that the “strict guidelines” around the amount of time and number of exercises risked turning the practice into a chore, rather than a supportive activity. Relatedly, feelings of guilt arose when participants were unable to complete all the assigned homework, which in turn diminished their sense of achievement.

Concerns were also raised about the body scan exercise, which some participants found particularly triggering in relation to gender dysphoria. As one noted, *“That first time doing a body scan is really rough.”* Another reflected, *“I think that’ll hit quite hard for people on the waiting list because becoming so aware of your body and focusing on it so much can trigger quite a lot of dysphoria, not just in the moment, but continuing along from it.”* This concern extended beyond individual experience: *“I think that made me sort of scared for other people. And maybe also a little bit for myself. But I was more thinking about, what if people here still are really dysphoric about that?”* To mitigate this, participants suggested introducing the concept of an anchor (e.g., focusing on the breath or external sounds) early in the program to provide a sense of safety and an alternative point of focus: *“In the future at least it’s good to introduce the concept of the anchor very early on.”*

These concerns underline the importance of careful implementation and communication, ensuring that mindfulness is presented as an optional and supportive tool, rather than an additional barrier or a replacement for essential gender-affirming care.

The experiences of the waiting list

This section presents key themes that emerged from semi-structured interviews conducted with participants. Each subsection highlights a specific problem area, illustrated with quotes from interviewees.

1. Long waiting times (3+ years, 1800+ people on the waiting list in the REGG)

- *“I was one of the lucky ones, having to wait for only two years.”*
- *“But I figured that was going to take way too long, because they take about three or four years.”*
- *“I think it’s going to be three years, right about now.”*

2. Little educated personnel

- *“A lot of these circulating stories tell that if you don’t fit neatly within either one of the binary categories [Female or Male], they [Healthcare] don’t really know what to do with it.”*
- *“I didn’t feel comfortable going to someone who probably would never understand what I was going through.”*
- *“Because there’s like a lot of lack of general knowledge about gender issues. So there’s plenty of people who end up on the waiting list who really don’t need to be there because they have other questions, but it’s conflated with [gender].”*

3. Unclarity of waiting periods

- *“Initially, the waiting list [time] would be around 56 weeks, but as I got through about 50 of those weeks, I got an update that it was gonna have to be a bit longer and they weren’t sure how long exactly. It ended up taking another year longer. They couldn’t give me updates throughout this whole year, so I was constantly in this sort of limbo of when I would actually get the help I needed.”*
- *“Like the first half year, I thought I might have to wait a year. And then I asked how much longer the list is. They replied something like three years.”*

4. Lack of communication between care providers and care-seekers

- *“There’s just nothing at all” [also in relation to support]*
- *“Nobody really checks in with you in between after you've been put on the waiting list.”*
- *“I had to get all of my information from other trans people. Nobody's giving me more info in this waiting time.”*
- *“Between that first letter of, ‘Hey, you're on the waiting list,’ and actually receiving the invite, I haven't noticed any communication.”*

5. Mental health deterioration

- *“I started out just feeling very low and depressed, especially at the start of the waiting list. As it kept going on longer, I started to notice a lot more suicidal thoughts. No suicide attempts, luckily, but I can't guarantee that if the waiting list had been any longer those would not have occurred.”*
- *“You just carry a lot of frustration with you, and you kind of feel like you're alone in this fight.”*
- *“Well, it feels kind of like you're on hold, right? Like everything is kind of paused.”*
- *“I noticed I was feeling so terrible being on that list and so anxious as well about, well: What if when they get through, they're not gonna believe that I’m actually trans? And they're going to deny me the health care.”*
- *“You know that something is wrong, but you can't do anything about it because nobody is offering to help with it.”*

The changes in body awareness and emotion regulation

The results from the interviews

Participants described significant challenges in identifying and processing their emotions before the intervention. One explained, *“When I do notice, I do not understand what I’m feeling,”* while another shared, *“I have a really hard time with [identifying positive emotions]. I can’t really tell those apart that well.”* Many spoke about emotional avoidance: *“I try to distance myself from it [emotions] and focus on other things,”* and *“Ignore all the sensations I was experiencing and just tune out as much of my body as possible.”* For some, this avoidance was tied to deep discomfort with their body: *“I not even had a mirror just to not see myself... troubled relationship with my body.”*

Negative emotions were often described as more intense and harder to recover from: *“The intensity of experiencing positive and negative emotions is not the same—negative emotions affect me stronger.”* This imbalance, combined with prolonged waiting periods, leaves individuals feeling overwhelmed (*“It’s like I feel drowning... I don’t even know where to start”*) and without effective coping tools (*“I’ve been avoiding them [emotions] for too long... I don’t really know another way [to deal with emotions besides distracting]”*).

In the interviews that came after the mindfulness training participants reported noticeable changes in their relationship with emotions and their bodies. Many described being better able to identify and understand what they were feeling. As one participant put it, *“I’ve been able to figure out like what I’m feeling and where that is in my body a lot better.”* Another added, *“I feel like now I can put it [positive emotions] into words more easily.”*

This improved recognition was linked to a stronger sense of control. One participant noted, *“I’m a bit more in control and that also allows me to have a better conversation about it. Otherwise, my emotions would have overtaken me.”* Others emphasized a new ability to stay present with difficult sensations, sharing that *“I feel like generally I’m a lot better able to cope with it and have these sensations sort of just be.”* Acceptance of bodily reactions also emerged as a theme. As one participant reflected, *“I’m starting to be okay with, like, with my body’s reactions, let’s say that, like with touches and stuff.”*

Several participants described becoming more emotionally available, *“I am more, more emotionally available to myself and to others,”* one participant explained. Others noted a shift in mindset towards greater openness: *“I’m trying to be a bit more open-minded about, okay, what if it’s not going to be bad? What if it’s going to be actually enjoyable?”*

Finally, participants highlighted a change in how they related to themselves internally. One participant described, *“The way I kind of have an internal dialogue with myself... It’s changed in tone, more compassionate, more kind, more patient.”*

In the table below, the overview of the changed themes from before (T0) to after the training (T2) are presented.

T0	T2
<i>Feeling overwhelmed and confused by bodily sensations</i>	<i>Being able to interpret the sensations and let them be</i>
<i>Always having low expectations (easily predictable reaction)</i>	<i>Allowing oneself to be open-minded (unpredictable reaction)</i>
<i>Feeling trapped in the body</i>	<i>Feeling more at home in the body</i>
<i>Not being able to differentiate between positive emotions</i>	<i>Differentiating between positive emotions and describing them</i>
<i>Paying attention to the body can trigger negative feelings (the funnel)</i>	<i>Paying attention to the body with reduced judgment and costs less energy</i>

The results from the questionnaires

Emotion regulation was assessed using the Difficulties in Emotion Regulation Scale (DERS, reference), and body awareness was measured using the Multidimensional Assessment of Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA, reference). At baseline (T0), participants reported greater difficulties in emotion regulation and lower interoceptive awareness compared to general population norms from the literature (references). As shown in Figures 3, DERS scores decreased throughout the training, approaching the population average, while all but one MAIA subscale showed improvement, indicating enhanced interoceptive ability (figures 4 and 5).

No statistically significant relationship between changes in emotion regulation and interoceptive awareness was established, likely due to the small sample size of this pilot. Statistical analysis of the remaining questionnaires, and their interrelations, is ongoing.

Figure 3. Difficulties in Emotion Regulation (DERS)

Fig. 3. Line graph visualizing decreasing mean DERS total scores with standard deviation whiskers across the three time points: baseline (T0), mid-training (T1), and post-training (T2). A dotted line represents general population sample mean score. Color bands indicate five severity ranges: Very high, High, Average, Low, and Very low.

Figure 4. Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA) line graph

Fig. 4. Line graph displaying eight MAIA subscale mean scores as a percentage of the total score of the subscale across the three measurement points: baseline (T0), mid-training (T1), and post-training (T2).

Figure 5. Interoceptive Awareness (MAIA) bar chart

Fig. 5. Bar graph presenting the mean scores and standard deviations for each of the eight MAIA subscales at the three time points: baseline (T0), mid-training (T1), and post-training (T2). The black dot with the horizontal line represents the mean score of the general population who haven't had an MBI for each subscale.

Analysis of alternatives

Description of alternatives

The alternatives described below should not be seen solely as replacements for the proposed mindfulness-based intervention. Depending on the needs of the population and available resources, some could function as viable stand-alone options, while others may be most effective when combined with mindfulness training to provide more comprehensive support.

1. **Break Buddy Program**

This peer support model would connect individuals further along in their transition—who have already received a gender dysphoria diagnosis and treatment—with those currently on waiting lists. Such a pairing could facilitate sharing lived experiences, offering emotional support, and reducing isolation. While promising, its effectiveness relies on oversight and involvement from care professionals to ensure safe and structured mentoring.

2. **AFFIRM Program**

AFFIRM is a structured, evidence-based CBT intervention developed by researchers in Toronto and South Florida, and translated into Dutch by Tim van de Grift (and colleagues). It is designed for LGBTQ2SIA+ youth and adults and explicitly incorporates modules on compassion, suicidality awareness, and minority stress. Educational in nature, AFFIRM is considered a potentially well-suited program to support mental well-being.

3. **De Wachtverzachter**

The Wachtverzachter is an informational document provided to individuals newly placed on the REGG waiting list. Its purpose is to promote “active waiting” by offering links to relevant resources, such as support organizations, informational materials, and community initiatives.

4. **Community-owned businesses**

Several TGD-led initiatives have emerged with the aim of supporting individuals in the early stages of their transition. These initiatives often address lifestyle, health, and well-being needs that may not be fully met within the formal healthcare system. For example, [HizzFit](#), a trans-led, Nijmegen-based organization, offers fitness and lifestyle coaching tailored to queer and transgender clients or a similar initiative in Rotterdam, [Queer Gym](#). Their services include queer group workouts and personal training. In addition, gender coaching practices such as [ZinVolledig praktijk](#) focus on the emotional and social aspects of navigating gender identity and transition. These services often provide individualized guidance, helping clients explore questions of identity, cope with stressors such as minority stress or dysphoria, and build resilience in daily life.

Constraints and political feasibility

Implementing alternative support methods for transgender individuals on waiting lists faces several constraints. First, the current global political climate presents challenges to advancing transgender healthcare initiatives. With broad systemic pressure on the healthcare system, transgender-specific care is not viewed as a priority, which limits available resources and policy attention. Institutional capacity is another constraint; for example, the Centre for Mindfulness is a relatively small organization, and expanding its operations to include regular additional and/or English-led groups would require structural changes and possible staffing increases. The integration of the AFFIRM program, while promising, would require local clinicians to become familiar with a new program that has a different focus compared to other psychological and mindfulness-based programs currently offered at the Centre for Mindfulness and Departments of psychiatry and medical psychology, creating a barrier to immediate implementation, but not to a long-term goal. Community-owned initiatives, such as HizzFit, also face accessibility challenges, as they are private businesses not covered by insurance, which potentially limits their reach to those with sufficient financial means.

Conclusions and recommendations – How to do research based on the pilot project

Recommendations

Next Step in the Project

- First, **further tailor the MBCT-L protocol and workbook** based on the insights from the first pilot and observations by facilitating trainers and participating researchers of the current pilot.
- Conduct a **second pilot** study with individuals on the waiting list using the revised mindfulness program.

What Should Be Continued?

- Include **semi-structured interviews** (especially in pilot #2).
- Ensure **two trainers** facilitate the training, with **at least one being a TGD person**.
- Continue using a **less formal communication style**, which has proven effective in participant engagement.

Participant Inclusion Considerations

- **Prioritize individuals with no mindfulness experience**, as they show greater benefit from learning new techniques; however, those with experience can still benefit depending on their current practice.
- Participants from the waiting list do not usually have a gender dysphoria diagnosis; therefore, there might be non-TGD participants.

Revised Mindfulness Program

- **Modify the body scan practice:**
 - Introduce an **anchor point** (e.g., breath, sound) before starting.
 - Consider **omitting or altering focus on chest and pelvic areas** in early sessions to avoid triggering gender dysphoria.
- Incorporate topics that address **transgender-specific emotional experiences**, including **gender dysphoria and euphoria**.
- Offer **more theoretical explanations** behind practices to support participants with anxiety or neurodiversity. That can ensure a more predictable and controllable environment.
- Add a "**Comeback Day**" after the training, where participants from all groups can reconnect and practice together.

Second Pilot Specifics

- Convert to **four time-point measurements** for data collection to capture the mid-point changes that commonly occur in the mindfulness program (T1) and the state of participants one month after finishing the training (T3).
- Replace **DSM-XC (self-report, reference)** with the **MINI (clinical interview, reference)** to better assess participants' mental health, especially since individuals with more severe symptoms may be included.
- Continue including a **researcher in the training group** to promote trust and horizontal communication between researchers and participants.
- Revise study documentation:
 - **Interview Guide:**
 - Add **questions** that are more intuitive and easier to interpret on emotional and body awareness.
 - Update questions about **waiting list experiences**.
 - **Informed Consent:**
 - **Initiate a discussion on ethical approaches to collecting** participant information in the informed consent process, particularly regarding **legal versus chosen names**. Some participants in the current study expressed discomfort with including their legal names ("deadnames") in documentation, as informed consent forms are retained for 15 years. Given that many individuals on the waiting list may not yet have legally changed their names, requiring the use of legal first names may evoke resentment or discomfort.
 - Add a clause on understanding what help the researchers can and cannot provide
 - **Participant Information Form (PIF):**
 - Add **details on data handling**, duration of storage, data types collected, and access protocols.

Towards a Larger-Scale Study

- Continue to use **self-report questionnaires** for outcome tracking.
- To expand the evidence base:
 - Consider adding **physiological measures**, such as **MRI-based tasks**.
 - Include **body awareness assessments**, e.g., the **heartbeat detection task** (see appendix).
- Reevaluate the **mindfulness training** content and **research protocols** following the second pilot before moving to full-scale implementation.

For illustration of the scale of the randomized control trial and the feasibility of the study see information below.

Considering an estimated effect size of the training is $d = 0.5$. to achieve sufficient statistical power, approximately 140 participants would be required to run a sufficiently powered RCT (70 per group: intervention vs. control), accounting for a 10% dropout rate.

With existing capacity at the Radboudumc Centre for Mindfulness (5 training seasons per year \times 8 groups per season \times 10–12 participants = 400–500 individuals annually), the study can be completed within two years if 1-2 groups per season can be repurposed for TransMind. Participants in the control group will be offered the training after their research participation is complete.

No new infrastructure is required, as the Centre for Mindfulness already has sufficient facilities and equipment.

Limitations

- **Limited Generalizability**
 - The pilot focuses on a specific subgroup: TGD individuals who have already completed their medical transition and identify as trans-feminine. Their experiences, resilience, and needs may differ from those currently on the waiting list.
 - Results may not fully translate to more vulnerable, younger, and trans-masculine individuals.
- **Possible staffing limitation**
 - The requirement for trainers with lived TGD experience narrows the pool of available facilitators.
- **Participant Selection Bias**
 - Individuals who self-select to participate may already be open to or interested in mindfulness, skewing results toward positive outcomes.
- **Dependence on Funding**
 - Sustained implementation would likely require ongoing funding from grants or insurers, which is not guaranteed, especially in a shifting political climate.

Unanticipated Consequences

- **Emotional Triggers**
 - Some mindfulness practices (e.g., body scans) may inadvertently intensify gender dysphoria if not properly adapted, especially in those earlier in transition. Even though it was possible to identify one of them in this pilot, other practices could still become triggering.
- **Equity and Access Issues**
 - Even though the training aims to be inclusive, not all participants may have equal access to the intervention (e.g., due to language barriers, disability, transportation, or digital exclusion for remote formats).
- **Community Pushback**
 - Some community members might perceive mindfulness as too clinical, too passive, or not aligned with their needs, especially if they favor more activist, peer-led, or trauma-informed approaches.

Conclusion

The pilot demonstrates promising potential for MBCT-L as a psychosocial support measure for TGD individuals facing extended waiting times. While further adaptation and testing are necessary, this approach offers a realistic and evidence-based way to mitigate the psychological harm caused by delays in accessing gender-affirming care.

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Appendices

Appendix 1. Resources and initiatives

- De Warme Wachtkamer: <https://www.humanistischverbond.nl/events/de-warme-wachtkamer-utrecht/>
- HizzFit: <https://hizzfit.nl>
- Queer Gym: <https://www.queergym.nl/nl/>
- Transgender Café Nijmegen: <https://www.transgendernijmegen.nl/cafe-avond/>
- Stichting Break Buddy: <https://www.instagram.com/stichtingbreakbuddy/?hl=en>
- ZinVolledig Praktijk: <https://www.zinvolledig.nl>

Appendix 2. The interview guides

Interview 1

Pre-interview

- Would you like some tea/coffee/water?
- How are you feeling?
- How did you experience the questionnaires?
- Do you currently have any questions?
- Are you ready to start the interview?

Introduction

Ask the participant to say that they consent to the recording after the start of the recording.

As we mentioned earlier, we are [our names], and we are interns working on the TransMind study. Through this interview, we want to better understand your personal experiences as a transgender or gender-diverse person—particularly in relation to your emotions and your connection with your body, and how mindfulness might or might not help you with this.

We're also interested in hearing about your experiences with being on the waiting list before receiving specialized care. This can be a challenging period, and we want to understand how it affected you, both emotionally and in terms of your relationship with your body.

- It is okay to take time to respond to the questions. But also to not answer them if you don't want to.

Do you have any questions now?

- To make sure we capture everything accurately, we would like to record this conversation. The recording will only be used for transcription and analysis within the research team. Would you be okay with that?

After the introduction say the participant number.

Interview 1. Section 1. Previous experience with transgender care

- **Can you tell us about your experience being on the waiting list for specialized transgender care?**
 - **In which time period were you on the waiting list?**
 - How did being on the waiting list impact your daily life?
 - What emotions did you experience while waiting for care?
 - Can you describe how informed and supported you felt during the waiting period?
 - What was your experience like in terms of guidance on what to expect while waiting?
- **What would have made your waiting experience better?**
 - **What did you do to help yourself?**
- **Is there anything else you would like us to know?**

Interview 1. Section 2. Mindfulness and body and emotional awareness?

- **How would you describe your relationship with your body?**
 - Are there moments when you feel more or less connected to your body? What influences that?
 - To what extent do you feel emotions in your body?
 - If you feel strong emotions, where in your body do you notice them?
 - What about the positive ones? (If they only mention negative emotions)
 - What are the body parts you feel more connected to?
 - Less connected to?
 - What do we say if asked to explain connectedness?
- **Is there anything else you would like us to know?**
- **How do you cope with emotions?**
 - Are there patterns that you have noticed?
 - Is this how you mostly cope?
 - What about positive emotions? (if they only tell about the negative emotions)?
- **Is there anything else you would like us to know?**
- *What are your thoughts or expectations about mindfulness?*
 - *How do you feel about starting mindfulness training?*

Distressing interview

- This was the last question.
- Do you have any questions?
 - [if not stop the recording]
- How are you feeling?
- What did you think about today?
- Thank the participant for their time.

Interview 2

Pre-interview

- Would you like some tea/coffee/water?
- How are you feeling right now?
- How did you experience the questionnaires?
- Do you currently have any questions?
- Are you ready to start the interview?
- To make sure we capture everything accurately, we would like to record this conversation. The recording will only be used for transcription and analysis within the research team. Would you be okay with that?

Introduction

Ask the participant to say that they consent to the recording after the start of the recording.

This is the last part of the study. We would like to ask you again about your emotions and your connection with your body, but now after you have completed the mindfulness training. We are also curious about your thoughts and experiences connected to the training. This is important for us to know so that we can adapt the training if needed for future use.

Do you have any questions?

After the introduction say the participant number.

Interview 2. Section 1. Body and emotional awareness

- **How would you describe your relationship with your body?**
 - o Are there moments when you feel more or less connected to your body? What influences that?
 - o To what extent do you feel emotions in your body?
 - If you feel strong emotions, where in your body do you notice them?
 - What about the positive ones? (If they only mention negative emotions)
 - o What are the body parts you feel more connected to?
 - o Less connected to?
 - What do we say if asked to explain connectedness?
- **Is there anything else you would like us to know?**
- **How do you cope with emotions?**
 - o Are there patterns that you have noticed?
 - o Is this how you mostly cope?
 - o What about positive emotions? (if they only tell about the negative emotions)?
- **Is there anything else you would like us to know?**

Interview 2. Section 2. Mindfulness intervention

- **What was your overall experience with the mindfulness training?**
- **What were the reasons for you to share or not share your experiences in the whole-group discussions?**
- **What should we keep in mind for the next group? (people on the waiting list)**
- **What did you think about the research procedures, interviews, questionnaires, communication?**
- **Is there anything else you would like us to know?**

Distressing interview

- This was the last question.
- Do you have any questions?
 - [if not stop the recording]
- How are you feeling?
- What did you think about today?
- Thank the participant for their time and participation in the study.